

PEERBY.COM

BORROW THE THINGS YOU NEED FROM THE PEOPLE IN YOUR NEIGHBORHOOD

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ABSTRACT

This design case reports the process of designing Peerby: an app and website that allows people to borrow the things they need from people in their neighborhood.

It describes how the product concept evolved from an inventory-listed peer-to-peer renting platform to a request-based borrowing and lending platform. We found out that people don't want to rent out things and ask their neighbors for money, but want to help out their neighbors for free. We learned that people are not willing to list their inventory to be able to lend their property, but when asked for a specific object people are very willing to help out a neighbor. We learned that trust and ratings aren't that important when it comes to neighbors and that people in general trust their neighbors easily. All these insights have led to a completely new product vision and design concept.

KEYWORDS: *social cohesion, sustainability, borrowing, platform, service*

INTRODUCTION

Peerby's founder, Daan Weddepohl, who owned a software company, saw his house burn down. In the fire, he lost all of his belongings. Watching the fire he asked himself: 'How did I end up owning all that stuff?' Left with his laptop as his only accessory and means of communication, he depended on the help and generosity of his friends in the weeks that followed.

To his surprise, they all loved to help him out! As a result, he spent valuable time with people he liked, and got to know them better in the process. 'Why don't we do this more often, if it's that easy and fun? Do I even still need stuff, if all I need is my laptop and the people around me?' he thought to himself. And the seed to create a business around this feeling of connectedness, sharing objects and kindness was planted.

This paper reports the design case of a Dutch Internet start up founded in 2011 called Peerby.com. Peerby is a platform that enables people to borrow things from people in their neighborhood. The start-up was founded in late 2011, and the first version went online October 2012. In little more than a year, it has grown to over 40,000 users worldwide, and over 3,000 borrowing transactions per month.

This paper will describe a few of the main insights that lead the design process and design decisions from that project up till today.

DESIGN

Approach

None of the 'designers' of the first version of Peerby were actually familiar with any design method, as they were not trained designers. When the author joined, it felt however as if the ViP approach was used almost religiously. The ViP (Vision in Product design) method introduced by Hekkert, and van Dijk (2011) is a context driven, human centred, interaction-based design approach. The main focus of the ViP approach is to look for alternatives, and possible futures, instead of solving present-day problems. It highly values the personal vision-creation of the designer (or team) and helps translate this vision into appropriate and suitable user-product interactions. As Peerby was founded by one person, and later created by a small team that shared the same vision, without restrictions in any design-brief or ideation phase whatsoever, the ViP method suited – and still does – our process very well.

After the first vision and conceptualizing phase, it was decided to create an MVP (minimal viable product), a working prototype that only contains the most important features and can be tested and used by real users. All the interaction is measured and from this data we acquire insights about how users behave using the product. Other insights are gained from talking to users and observing behaviour. In software development this method is called the 'Lean Start-up method' (Ries, E. 2011). The knowledge and insights gained from this version are used to build new and improved features, and the team constantly iterates these "build-measure-learn" loops in order to improve the product.

For this paper I will only focus on a few key emotional & psychological insights that have been of great influence on the product concept. I will describe how these factors translated in the product concept and main interactions as well as some new insights that we gained along the way.

First concept - A Peer to Peer Renting Platform

Weddephohls' vision was to create a platform where people that live close to each other can help each other out by sharing the things they own. Initially, the assumption was that people would only do that if they could earn a small sum of money in return. So the first concept of Peerby was a renting platform. Users could list the items that they owned and were willing to rent out, and request any item they needed by typing in the name of the item. The request would then be sent out to all the Peerby users in the neighborhood who had

listed the item. The owner would then be able to chat with the requester to complete the transaction.

MVP - Minimal Viable Product

The first concept was quite elaborate, with features like personal profiles, ratings, product profiles, max radius settings, etc. The Lean start-up method tells you to first create a minimal viable product, in order to test the principles and hypothesis your concept is based on, before spending months developing something that turns out wrong. So, we decided to first create a very simple web-based version of the platform. The payment-method was left out, and people were encouraged to arrange their own prices and deals. Since it was only the very beginning of Peerby, no inventory was listed yet, so it wasn't possible to search for products intelligently by going through peoples' listings. It was decided for now to just send out emails to Peerby-members of everything that was requested until the listing-of-items-system was built and people had had the time to list their inventory. The only two basic functions that were developed were:

1. users could create a request of what they wanted to rent.
2. they could receive requests from neighbors, both through email and on the website at the 'incoming requests' tab (see Figure 04).

For each new request an email was sent to the closest 100 Peerby members, and users could answer "yes", "no" or "not now". If a user answered "yes", she and the requestor would end up in a chat.

Figure 1. Listing the items you would like to rent out.

Figure 2. Requesting an item you would like to rent.

Figure 3. People could send out a request and write something nice to convince their neighbors to lend them something.

Figure 4. Users could receive requests from their neighbors and answer them.

Learnings

From this first product-version we learned many important things about our users that profoundly shaped our product vision, and the next version in particular. A few of the main psychological insights are explained here.

1. People don't want to rent things to their neighbors, they want to help and meet their neighbors.

We encouraged people to rent out things to their neighbors, but they didn't. By analyzing peoples' chats, we learned that almost no one asked for money. The assumption that people need something in return for their helping a neighbor just wasn't valid. Instead we saw that people loved to help out their neighbors. Very often, people got more than three neighbors willing to lend a requested item. Users told us that they liked meeting new neighbors and doing something nice for them. When it comes to neighbors, it turns out people are in fact very altruistic.

2. People don't want to spend time listing their inventory, but when asked, they love to help out, with anything.

People responded very positively to the 'random' requests that we sent out and relatively few people asked us to list their items.

When we looked into it, every single platform we could find that tried to create a borrowing/lending service failed. On average people listed less than one item per member. This is based on an analysis we performed of the borrowing/lending platforms spullendelen.nl, neighborrow.com, neighborgoods.net, and streetbank.com. We did this by dividing the number of members by the number of listed items. The result was always less than one.

Thinking of the proverbial cup of sugar, 'normal' borrowing usually happens only when the borrower experiences an often sudden need, and asks his or her neighbor for a favor. From the lender's perspective, if the favor is granted, the deed is reactive rather than proactive. It seems like people do like to help out someone in need, but are not very willing to spend a lot of time anticipating that possibility.

In fact, when you think about the process of borrowing, how often does one wonder, going over all the things in and around the house, 'Gosh, I wish someone would come and borrow these things from me'?

By creating a platform that was request based, we tapped into something that did work and suited the borrowing/lending principles much better.

Figure 5. Streetbank. On average people never list more than one item to lend.

Figure o6. Screenshots of the current iOS app

3. Trust – people naturally trust their neighbors and violation occurs very seldom.

The first Peerby concept had a very elaborate trust and rating system. People were able to report other users in case of violation, and review/rate their neighbors. People could leave a deposit. In the MVP there were no such things. The product was in that sense very ‘risky’ and open. To our surprise, people didn’t care that much. Usually borrowers (people that sent out a request) were already so pleased by the kind offers of their neighbors that that was enough to trust someone. And lenders were also very willing to help out, without knowing anything about the other member. ‘Rating’ a person that just lent you something for free, didn’t quite fit the situation. We did, however, discover that borrowers felt a strong need to publicly (on a profile) thank the lender for his/her kindness. Also publishing how long someone had been a member, along with her activity also made sense. Of all the transactions that we had on the platform (over 10.000), we know of only three cases where things were not returned or broken and left unresolved.

4. People fear being rejected when asking for a favor directly.

In ‘real life’ as a borrower, you have to ask your neighbor for a favor. You have to go over, ring a bell and ask for something. By directly asking this favor, one runs the risk of being a burden to your neighbor or your neighbor just not being willing to lend you something and thus being rejected. This anticipated feeling of discomfort makes borrowing a rather risky and therefore potentially uncomfortable action and this could contribute to people borrowing less than they would like to. The market-place inventory model for borrowing and lending does not change that; you need to ask your neighbors (whom you don’t know) for a favor directly, by personally requesting an item, running the risk of being rejected. But the way we sent out our requests (to 100 people) avoided this risk. Because as a borrower you would not know who was asked (we don’t give that feedback) and people could freely say NO without insulting someone. The borrower is only notified about the few people that said yes and this is only a very positive experience.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION – A REQUEST-BASED BORROWING AND LENDING PLATFORM

From a peer-to-peer renting service, Peerby has evolved in the only working borrowing/lending platform in the world. We learned a huge amount from our first version of the product, and we are now planning to build a completely revised mobile (android) version of the app. The focus on borrowing, and the request-based interaction, have become key. The open system based on trusting your neighbors (i.e., no ratings) is also very important. We have also learned about what people think is still missing in the product. For example, people want to know what is happening on Peerby in their neighborhood. They want to interact in more ways than just saying “yes”, “no” or “not now” to their neighbors’ needs. In some cases they do want to list special items. And, most of all, people want to be inspired by being able to ‘browse’ through things they could possibly borrow. Our main short-term challenge will be to stimulate people to request things and make borrowing from their neighbors a new habit. We learned that people love to lend. Our transaction success rate at the moment is 83%! Another challenge is to create a self-learning inventory system so that we can search in smarter ways and thus improve fulfillment even further.

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URLS

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